

**PREMIERE –
PREPARING MULTI-
ACTOR PROJECTS
IN A CO-CREATIVE WAY**

GA No. 101086531

**FINAL REPORT of PREMIERE Focus Group #2:
Advancing evaluation of the multi-
actor approach (MAA)**

December 2024 – March 2025

MAIN AUTHORS

Jordi Pietx
Mark Redman

WITH CONTRIBUTIONS FROM

Participants to the Focus Group
Susanne v. Münchhausen (Project Co-ordinator)
All partner teams

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Funded by
the European Union

The responsibility for the information and views set out in this document lies entirely with the authors and not with the European Commission or its services.

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Long Form
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy of the EU
CR	Consensus Report
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
DG	Directorate-General of the European Commission
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research, Technology and Digitalisation
EC	European Commission
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FG	Focus Group
F&T	EU Funding & Tenders
H2020	Horizon 2020
HEU	Horizon Europe
IA	Innovation Action
MA	Multi-Actor
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
NCP	National Contact Point
OG	EIP-AGRI Operational Group
R&I	Research and Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SEP	Submission and Evaluation of Proposals (online tool)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report, prepared by the PREMIERE project, is based on the results of the Focus Group “Advancing evaluation of the multi-actor approach (MAA)” conducted between December 2024 and April 2025, in collaboration with the European Commission. The Focus Group focused on MAA evaluation in Horizon Europe Cluster 6, but it is acknowledged that these recommendations should be extended to, and further developed for, Horizon Mission Soil, Horizon Partnerships, and others (e.g. PRIMA-MED).

The report presents the context, recommendations and support materials to strengthen the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) within Horizon Europe by improving its evaluation. Clarity and consistency for the MAA are fundamental principles in this process.

The focus group process involved **23 participants**, representing policy officers (AGRI, ENV, MARE), REA project officers, NCPs, external experts, and project participants. They responded to an initial survey, met online on 23 January 2025 and continued with online discussions contributing to draft recommendations in April 2025 that were subsequently presented and discussed with European Commission officers in May 2025.

The report consists of **three sections**: i) an introduction to the objectives and scope of the Focus Group; ii) a description of the Focus Group process; and; iii) actionable recommendations from the Focus Group for strengthening evaluation of MAA project in the short- (2025), medium- (2026-2027), and longer-term (post-2028).

A total of **nine framework recommendations** are presented together with sub-recommendations, plus indications on **complementary materials** to facilitate and support implementation of the recommendations. These include new briefing slides for evaluators, specific MAA questions for topic evaluation grids and an introductory video, amongst others. Some of these support materials are presented in full content format (briefing slides, evaluation grid, procedure to include the MAA in ‘scope’ topic texts), while others are outlined for future development.

1 INTRODUCTION

In addition to the destinations and topics selected as priorities for research and innovation (R&I) actions, the Horizon Europe (HEU) framework programme (2021-2027) promotes a range of cross-cutting R&I approaches. Examples of the cross-cutting R&I approaches that are commonly flagged in Cluster 6 topic descriptions include:

- Social sciences and humanities (SSH)
- Gender dimension
- Open science
- Social innovation
- Multi-actor approach (MAA)
- Involvement of the Joint Research Council

These cross-cutting approaches can be mandatory when mentioned (SSH and MAA); optional (JRC involvement); overarching across all HEU (Gender dimension and Open science), or specific to a topic text (Social innovation). If these cross-cutting R&I approaches are mentioned in a topic description, they **are considered as part of the evaluation process**.

There was some initial consideration of MAA evaluation in the first PREMIERE Focus Group entitled ‘Programming and Implementation of the MAA’ that was organized in May-June 2024.

Figure 1: The ‘nested problems’ for the MAA, as identified by the PREMIERE Focus Group 1 on Programming and Implementation of the MAA.

This framed MAA evaluation within a set of “nested problems” (see **Figure 1**) whereby a **lack of clear and consistent understanding of the MAA** is (amongst other things) manifested in inconsistent and potentially ineffective evaluation of the MAA, whereby evaluators are accepting without scoring down some project proposals that have an incomplete inclusion of the MAA.

This observation is broadly in line with the findings of a recent independent review of proposal evaluation processes in Horizon 2020¹, which concluded:

“To ensure consistency in assessment of applications, it is important to have clarity and consensus on the rules and assessment criteria associated with the evaluation. Evidence from the literature suggests there may be a lack of clarity on how criteria – particularly the ‘Excellence’ criterion – should be implemented and that reviewers may not always be following action-specific guidance provided.”

1.1 Focus Group Objectives and Scope

The theme of ‘**Advancing evaluation of the Multi-actor Approach**’ within Horizon Europe projects was chosen in consultation with EC colleagues from DG AGRI (Unit F2 – Research and Innovation) in light of the upcoming evaluations for the 2025 and 2026-2027 Work Programmes and beyond.

The working question for discussion was:

*“How can the implementation (and ultimate impact) of the multi-actor approach (MAA) be further **strengthened by improving its evaluation**?”*

The Focus Group aimed to engage with relevant key actors and stakeholders in a co-creative process to:

- **Share views and experiences** regarding the current state of HEU multi-actor (MA) project proposal evaluation with a specific focus on the identification and briefing of evaluators, eligibility check of proposals, execution of the evaluation process, and the drafting and communication of ESR content—what’s currently working well / less well?
- **Identify and prioritise specific opportunities** for improving the quality/effectiveness of HEU multi-actor (MA) project proposal evaluation

¹ Rodriguez-Rincon, D., Feijao, C., Stevenson, C. et al. (2022). *Study on the proposal evaluation system for the EU R&I framework programme – Final report*. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/16211>

- **Elaborate actionable recommendations** for improving the quality/effectiveness of multi-actor (MA) project proposal evaluation during the remaining period of the HEU framework programme (2025-2027)
- **Develop a longer-term vision** for the role of evaluation in enlarging and strengthening the MAA in future R&I framework programmes, notably FP10 (2028-2034).

It is important to note that a key opening perspective of this Focus Group was that developments in applying the MAA in Horizon Europe are **already moving in the right direction** and are strengthening the approach step-by-step. The Focus Group set out to **build upon these positive developments**, whilst also acknowledging:

1. Reflections amongst some experienced stakeholders that the MAA risks being perceived as a popular or fashionable approach for Horizon topics. Notably, that some topics are being flagged as needing to apply the MA without explanation of WHY it is required, thereby creating uncertainty and a lack of precision in the evaluation process.
2. The importance of keeping MAA evaluation as precise and straightforward as possible to avoid creating additional burden for evaluators, or at least, to ensure that improvements in the quality of the MAA evaluation outcomes can convincingly justify any extra burden generated.
3. Under Horizon Europe (HEU), the MAA is increasingly applied under **Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment)**, plus the work programmes of the **Horizon Soil Mission** and the calls of **several Horizon Partnerships**, including those on Agroecology, Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and associated programmes like PRIMA in the Mediterranean region.

Whilst these different funding calls share the MAA concept; the precise definition of the MAA varies between them. This report, and the recommendations contained in it, refer specifically to the MAA definition for Cluster 6 (*Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment*) and not to other programmes and partnerships.

2 FOCUS GROUP PROCESS

The participants in the Focus Group were selected and invited following multi-actor principles framed by the Quadruple-helix model and the different actor types related to MA proposal development and evaluation. Gender and geographical distribution were also considered.

The list of the 23 Focus Group participants is available in [Annex 1](#).

All participants were invited to contribute to a progressive co-creation process involving the following steps:

- **Initial survey** of basic questions as part of the registration procedure for the Focus Group (15 respondents).
- Reading and reflecting on a **Background Document** in preparation for the Focus Group meeting, including the identification of additional key challenges and solutions relevant to the Focus Group discussions.
- An **online Focus Group session** held on 23 January 2025 (23 participants) to agree on the main challenges and solutions and to scope recommendations in three broad areas:
 - i. A better framework for improving the quality/effectiveness of HEU MAA evaluation (2025-2027)
 - ii. Selecting and supporting evaluators for HEU MAA evaluation (2025-2027)
 - iii. A vision for the role of evaluation in strengthening the MAA in FP10 (2028-2034).
- **Drafting of recommendations** for the *Focus Group Final Report*, plus a selection of additional supporting materials.
- **Online presentation** of Focus Group recommendations to European Commission officers on 16 May 2025.
- **Finalisation** of *Focus Group Report* and supporting materials, notably an extended set of briefing slides for evaluators.

3 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING EVALUATION OF THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH (MAA)

The following recommendations for improving the quality and effectiveness of MAA evaluation have been developed from the outcomes of the Focus Group discussions, plus additional comments and feedback from participants.

They respond to four clusters of specific needs identified during the Focus Group:

- i) Need for a **better explanation** of the MAA for evaluators and rapporteurs, taking into account that many have no MAA experience.
- ii) Specific need for **clearer justification** of WHY the MAA requirement is included in the topic text.
- iii) Need for **more explicit guidance** on how to evaluate the MAA fairly, effectively and consistently.
- iv) Need for **broader, more systemic revision** of the MAA.

The recommendations are divided into **short-** and **medium-term with** specific indications regarding their immediate applicability in relation to the 2025 and 2026-2027 HEU Work Programmes, and **longer-term**, with a view towards the next Framework Programme (FP10) starting in 2028.

It is intended that the recommendations are **actionable**, not merely hypothetical. Additional comments are included for some recommendations, including observations on their **feasibility**.

3.1 Short-term recommendations (2025)

Recommendation #1:

Enhance the general understanding of the MAA definition / specific requirements among EC and REA officers, NCPs, applicants, and external evaluators. Specifically, **provide a better explanation of the MAA for evaluators and more explicit guidance from EC services** on how to evaluate the MAA more consistently and objectively.

This can be pursued most rapidly with a comprehensive update of the REA ‘topic briefing slides’ used to guide evaluators of the 2025 MAA proposal submissions. It is recommended that the briefing slides:

1. Refer evaluators to **all available materials** about the MAA, including those recently produced by PREMIERE²
2. **More clearly explain** how the MAA is currently addressed as BOTH an additional eligibility criterion and an excellence criterion (whilst stressing the need to avoid the risk of double-penalisation), including:
 - **Clear indication** of how the seven specific requirements of the MAA are a) linked to the three main evaluation criteria (Excellence, Impact, and Quality and Efficiency of Implementation) and b) therefore expected to be found in the three sections of Part B, as well as indicated in Part A and the budget.
 - **Clear instruction** that if the MAA requirements are NOT met under each of the relevant evaluation criteria, this must be counted as a SIGNIFICANT WEAKNESS under the Excellence criterion and thereby trigger a below threshold score.
3. Reinforce existing checks by REA on consortium composition and the distribution of staff effort, with an **additional specific requirement** that all components of the application, including Parts A and B, plus the budget, must be consistent with the MAA. Note that lump sum topics already require a more detailed overview of the proposed budget to illustrate more precisely the engagement of partners in the project activities.
4. Provide **good examples of ESR statements** (positive and negative) for meaningful feedback to applicants about the completeness of the MAA in their proposals

Annex 2 contains an **expanded set of briefing slides** proposing detailed instructions for guiding the evaluation of MAA proposals in five steps:

Step 1: Study the key topic information

Step 2: Ensure you have a common understanding of the MAA definition in your group of evaluators

Step 3: Identify the relevant multi-actor-specific elements in each proposal

² PREMIERE has prepared an expanded Q&A including 17 basic questions on the MAA. This is currently available as a document on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/14196006>) and as a dedicated section on the PREMIERE website (<https://premiere-multiactor.eu/academy/maa-q-and-a/>). Ideally, this Q&A should be part of a European Commission webpage dedicated to the MAA, similarly to other Horizon requirements and cross-cutting themes like gender, SSH or Open Science.

Step 4: Score the identified multi-actor elements of individual proposals

Step 5: Make final decision regarding the additional eligibility condition and agree on ESR statements

The full set of extended briefing slides have been shared with the EC and REA colleagues in the Focus Group for their consideration.

3.2 Medium-term recommendations (2026-2027)

Recommendation #2:

Establish the **basis for strengthened MAA evaluation** by requiring topic writers to include a specific statement in all MAA topic texts explaining WHY the topic requires the MAA and WHAT is expected as “*genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors*” in that specific project type (RIA, IA or CSA) and topic.

Annex 3 presents a proposal for instructions addressed to topic drafters/writers with indications on how to present and describe the specific need and context for the MAA in a particular topic. These instructions aim to define concise and precise texts for the MAA in each topic, thereby staying in line with the more compact topic descriptions required from 2026.

All MAA topic **call texts should be reviewed after initial drafting** to ensure clarity, consistency, and alignment with the MAA definition. Inclusion of the MAA requirement must be clearly justifiable, and a specific mechanism for recommending re-drafting should be introduced.

This might eventually include creating a figure of "Coordinator / Advisor on the MAA" for the topic drafting units, to supervise the process of MAA labelling of work programme topics, and/or establishing an editorial board for the call topic drafting process, consisting of EC/REA officers from relevant units.

Recommendation #3:

Incorporate the updated Briefing Slides into the *Guide for Evaluators & Rapporteurs* in the ‘Supporting Documents’ section of the SEP Dashboard³. This comprehensive guide is not publicly available and details all information

³ Tasks as an evaluator are conducted via the EC’s online tool called SEP (Submission and Evaluation of Proposals). This is used to access proposals and to write and submit evaluation reports.

regarding the entire evaluation process. The content of the *Guide* is regularly updated and refined, and it is intended to be the **main reference document for evaluators**.

Guidance on MAA evaluation could be further enhanced with examples of the **full scope of MAA implementation** that may be encountered by evaluators, including for different project types (RIAs, IAs and the numerous variants of CSA).

Recommendation #4:

Collaborate with PREMIERE to **prepare a short guidance video** on MAA evaluation.

Evaluation guidance videos are available via the F&T Portal for key cross-cutting issues⁴ - for example, a 6-minute video has recently been posted (July 2025) on 'How to evaluate Social Sciences and Humanities in Horizon Europe proposals':

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=POithrsc5Hc&ab_channel=EUScience%26Innovation .

According to REA colleagues, it is unlikely that a similar video could be produced by the central services of DG RTD for the MAA. However, if the necessary resources are available, this creates a potential opportunity for the PREMIERE project.

Suggested elements for a video script are:

- Definition and relevance of the MAA in Horizon Europe.
- How and where to consider the MAA in the proposal template.
- Indicative examples of good application of the MAA

⁴ See the evaluation guidance videos at the bottom of the page here: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/videos/support>

3.3 Longer-term recommendations (2028-2034)

Recommendation #5:

It is understood that the MAA is not identified as a cross-cutting horizontal principle in the draft FP10 Regulation⁵ and is not, therefore, being considered as applicable to all parts of Horizon Europe. However, it **should be given greater visibility in anticipation of its growing significance and potential** for more widespread adoption in specific areas of the post-2028 R&I programme.

All official documents regarding the MAA should be available and more easily findable by applicants and evaluators in the F&T portal. This includes the Q&A already mentioned in Recommendation #1.

Information on the MAA could be included in the ‘Reference documents’ section of the F&T portal⁶, together with updated and more clearly presented information on the DG RTD website⁷. At the time of writing (July 2025), there is no dedicated webpage for the MAA – only outdated information on the EIP-AGRI⁸ and an old link (pre-April 2023) to the CAP Network website⁹.

Recommendation #6:

Initiate a robust and objective review of the MAA to a) strengthen understanding of the efficacy of the approach and b) enhance its programming and implementation. Potential elements to consider include:

- Introduction of the MAA as an additional eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe was intended to enhance its visibility and promote its application, but is this additional criterion being effectively applied and thereby improving the quality of MAA projects being funded?
- Does the existing definition of the MAA require simple refinement or a more substantive update? Can each ‘specific requirement’ of the MAA be more clearly transposed into criterion for evaluation? Should the specific

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0543>

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents?programmePeriod=2021-2027&frameworkProgramme=43108390>

⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas/interactive-innovation-and-eip-agri_en

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/multi-actor-projects-scientists-and-farmers.html>

requirements of the MAA be simplified? For example, to require a single complete description of the ‘Application of the MAA’¹⁰, either as a separate document or a discrete annex of Part B of the common application forms.

- Is it feasible to update application forms and evaluation templates to more appropriately accommodate the MAA?

For example, **Annex 4** presents a proposal to include a limited extra content to the topic evaluation grid template to be used in MAA topics. It is not a new and separate grid but an addition to the existing evaluation grid with new content highlighted in orange text in the annex.

- Can the evaluation process be strengthened with a clearer understanding and definition of MAA **shortcomings** and **weaknesses** in different project types?

Recommendation #7:

Consider using an ‘assessment rubric’ as a complementary tool to support evaluation of the MAA.

‘Assessment rubrics’ are a commonly used tool in education for evaluating student learning by comparing it against a standard or benchmark¹¹, whereby a rubric “*articulates the expectations for assignments and performance tasks by listing criteria, and for each criterion, describing levels of quality*”. A similar approach could be used to support a more consistent evaluation of the MAA in project proposals.

PREMIERE has produced a preliminary *Rubric for MAA Evaluation* based on an analysis of MAA-related ESRs and two examples of related rubrics¹². This first version is based upon nine different principles derived from the MAA definition, plus three specific principles for the drafting of ESRs. Each principle is evaluated on a scale of 1-5 in the rubric.

¹⁰ For example, applicants could be required to explicitly explain how the MAA has been applied during proposal preparation and will subsequently be applied during project implementation, with evidence of the involvement of each actor in the context of the project’s concept and the topic’s requirements. Details to be provided would include how actors were involved in preparatory meetings, the development of the proposal, and other relevant activities

¹¹ For further details on the use of assessment rubrics, see:

<https://teaching.berkeley.edu/teaching-guides/assessing-learning/assessment-rubrics>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/8377184>

An MAA evaluation rubric does not need to be complex. Even with less details than the preliminary version produced by PREMIERE, it could be a useful tool for applicants, as well as for evaluators, for fine-tuning and strengthening application of the MAA.

Recommendation #8:

The expertise of external experts contracted to evaluate MAA project proposals was identified by the Focus Group as a significant factor influencing the quality of MAA evaluations.

Both REA and contracted experts should have a **clear understanding** of the theoretical and practical knowledge that MAA evaluators are expected to provide. A (voluntary) **MAA Competence Framework** would provide such clear and consistent reference for selecting evaluators for MAA topics, for example based on the European Competence Framework for Research Managers¹³.

A competence framework allows to identify the core skills and competencies needed for effective performance of a job or a professional activity. It provides a structured approach for individuals and organisations, offering a consistent standard for roles in a certain area of work. A competence enables self-assessment, highlights skill gaps, and guides professional development¹⁴.

The EC is currently using competence frameworks in several areas including research managers, digital, sustainability, entrepreneurship and others. The example of Error! Reference source not found. shows how a competence framework allows to identify relevant skills and competences and define a progressive level of expertise, thus allowing the aforementioned self-assessment. REA officers would also have a clearer definition of the more adequate profiles of experts.

¹³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/rm-comp-european-competence-framework-research-managers_en

¹⁴ See the webpage of the Research Managers Competence Framework: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/rm-comp-european-competence-framework-research-managers_en#other-eu-competence-frameworks

COGNITIVE ABILITIES/PERSONAL ATTRIBUTES

3. Cultural Sensitivity

Awareness and respect for diverse cultural perspectives, values, and norms. Fostering an inclusive work environment, acknowledging the impact of cultural nuances on research design and implementation.

FOUNDATIONAL	INTERMEDIATE	ADVANCED	EXPERT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic understanding of the importance of cultural sensitivity in diverse research environments. • Has a fundamental awareness of cultural differences, customs and traditions. • Communicates respectfully through all forms of communication. • Exhibits understanding towards individuals from different cultural backgrounds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans and delivers effective cross-cultural communication in all interactions with collaborators, partners, and team. • Exhibits cultural intelligence and awareness whilst working with diverse research teams and/or other teams. • Recognises and addresses any issues through unintended behaviours. • Demonstrates the ability to navigate and communicate effectively in diverse cultural contexts, displaying awareness, respect, and adaptability towards varying cultural norms and practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fosters a culturally diverse and inclusive environment within the research team and/or other teams. • Successfully interacts in cross-cultural research collaborations and partner consortiums. • Empowers cultural differences via the establishment of procedures and strategies within the research team and/or other teams. • Exhibits the ability to seamlessly navigate diverse cultural environments, fostering inclusive interactions, and contributing positively to crosscultural collaborations with a high degree of cultural awareness and empathy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides expert level advice to senior management and organisational leadership to enhance research and organisational cultural sensitivity. • Develop and implement cultural sensitivity strategies at team, organisation, national and or international level. • Displays advanced skills in fostering cross-cultural understanding, resolving cultural conflicts, and serving as a catalyst for inclusive environments through insightful leadership and mentorship. • Demonstrates exceptional proficiency in understanding, respecting, and navigating complex cultural dynamics.

Figure 2: Example of a component for a competence framework showing a spectrum from basic (Foundational) to Expert

The development of an MAA Competence Framework would include:

- Identifying the relevant skills and competences.
- Defining the range of expertise for each of these.
- Publish and disseminate the competence framework, improving and adapting it overtime.

The PREMIERE Rubric for the multi-actor approach follows a similar approach to a competence framework and could be used for its development.

Recommendation #9:

Finally, it is recommended that REA make greater use of existing procedures to strengthen the MAA. This includes a) the **Grant Agreement negotiations and DoA preparation** (e.g. taking account of ESR comments generated in the evaluation phase), and b) **the monitoring of the MAA during periodic review** (e.g. with a specific question in the review report template to ensure greater compliance with the expectations of the MAA described in the original topic text and included in the DoA).

ANNEX 1: Focus Group Participants

Name	Organisation	Country
Andrew Fieldsend	Independent	Hungary
Anna Bagó	Beta Centre, University of Vic	Catalonia, Spain
Cristina Micheloni	AIAB (Associazione Italiana Agricoltura Biologica)	Italy
Lauriane Mariane	IZSLT B-THENET	Italy
Marta Conde	CDTI	Spain
Mikelis Grivins	Baltic Studies Centre	Latvia
Siavash Farahbakhsh	ILVO	Flanders, Belgium
Sonja Karoglan	Ecologica	Croatia
Veronica Manara	IZSLT	Italy
Vesna Miličić	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia	Slovenia
Alberto Pozza	REA - EC	European Commission
Ana Patricia López Blanco	DG AGRI	European Commission
Astrid Guiffart	REA - EC	European Commission
Dacil Unzué	REA	European Commission
Francisco de Asis Sánchez Crespo	DG ENV	European Commission
Goran Kumric	REA - EC	European Commission
Isabelle Van Borm	DG AGRI	European Commission
Natalia Brzezina	DG AGRI	European Commission
Nikos Zampoukas	DG RTD	European Commission
Noa Sainz	DG RTD	European Commission
Pilar Llorente Ruiz de Azua	Circular-BioBased Europe JU	European Commission
Rodrigo Ataide	DG MARE	European Commission
Ruska Kelevska	REA - EC	European Commission

ANNEX 2: Proposed Briefing Slides for MAA Evaluators and Rapporteurs

This annex is an updated set of the **pre-prepared MAA slides** that are used by REA for the topic-specific briefing meeting of experts prior to the start of evaluation.

The slides are also available in pptx format.

Proposed slide set for the briefing of external evaluators:

How to evaluate the multi-actor approach (MAA)?

This slide set is proposed by the PREMIERE project team to address the need for more **detailed and definitive guidance** for external experts on how to evaluate proposals submitted for topics that include the additional eligibility condition to follow the multi-actor approach.

It is based on the results of a Focus Group process on multi-actor evaluation, organised as an online consultation process in cooperation with DG-AGRI (January-May 2025).

This document presents the view of the authors and not of the European Commission. However, the Commission and its Services are welcome to include the content in their official communication material.

1

Evaluating the multi-actor approach (MAA) in 5 steps

Step 1: Study the key topic information

Step 2: Ensure you have a common understanding of the MAA definition in your group of evaluators

Step 3: Identify the relevant multi-actor-specific elements in each proposal

Step 4: Score the identified multi-actor elements of individual proposals

Step 5: Make final decision regarding the additional eligibility condition and agree on ESR statements

2

Step 1: Study the key topic information

Does the call topic Specific Conditions box include the multi-actor approach (MAA) as an additional eligibility criterion?

If yes, the application of the MAA is a legal requirement to receive funding

Does the call topic text include specific highlight further specific details about application of the MAA in proposals?

If yes, these details provide additional information e.g. why this topic is flagged as MAA. However, all general MA requirements continue to apply.

Responsibility of the evaluators

- Evaluators must score the MAA a) taking account of both Parts A and B of an application; b) under all three evaluation criteria (Excellence, Impact and Implementation), and; c) whilst taking care to avoid double or triple penalisation.
- Based on this assessment, evaluators must state if the MAA additional eligibility criterion is met.
- Multi-Actor Topic applications are only eligible for funding when i) the criteria scores are above the required thresholds, and ii) the evaluators agree that the MAA additional eligibility criterion is fulfilled.

3

The application and evaluation of the multi-actor approach (MAA) is complex

More information on the MAA is available here:

- Link to the official text describing the MAA
- Links to relevant videos, webinars etc.
- Etc.

4

Step 2: Ensure you have a common understanding of the MAA definition in your group of evaluators

- The MAA is a form of interactive, transdisciplinary and responsible research and innovation (R&I).
- It aims to make the R&I process more co-creative and, thereby, ensure its outcomes are more co-owned, reliable, demand-driven and relevant to society.
- Multi-Actor (MA) projects ensure the genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors in co-creation. The cooperation of actors with complementary competencies helps achieve the jointly agreed-upon objectives.
- Co-creation between academic actors and actors with practice orientation takes place all along the project, from proposal preparation, throughout project implementation and beyond. This helps to ensure impact.

5

Multi-actor project proposals must demonstrate how:

1. The description of the project concept, including the proposed objectives, activities and planning, are targeting the needs/challenges/opportunities for the (end-)users of the project results;
2. The composition of the consortium fits into the project concept and reflects a balanced choice of relevant actors who have complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical, etc.) and skills to achieve the project objective, and to ensure that project results are ready for practice and broadly implemented;
3. The project intends to use existing practices and tacit knowledge. This should be illustrated in the proposal methodology with a sufficient number of high-quality knowledge exchange activities outlining the precise and active roles of the different, relevant non-scientific actors in the co-creation and sharing of R&I contents. The cross-fertilisation of skills, experiences, competencies and ideas between actors should generate innovative findings and solutions that are more likely to be widely applied in practice;

* These are the seven MA requirements that apply to Horizon Europe Cluster 6

6

Multi-actor project proposals must demonstrate how:

4. The project will facilitate the multi-actor engagement process by making use of the most appropriate methods and expertise, and what mechanisms the project will set up to maintain engagement of different, relevant actors, in particular non-scientific actors, during the whole project lifecycle;
5. The project has added-value for the (end-)users and how it will complement and advance the state-of-the-art, including existing knowledge and best practices;
6. The project will result in practical and ready to use knowledge, solutions, approaches, tools, products, processes or services that are easily understandable and accessible for (end-)users;
7. These results ready for practice will be widely and effectively disseminated, and feed into the existing dissemination channels most consulted and trusted by the (end-)users of the project results in countries and regions.

* These are the seven MA requirements that apply to Horizon Europe Cluster 6

Understanding the term 'Actor' within the MAA

The "ladder of multi-actor participation"

Level 1 actors: Co-creation processes involving the **main consortium actors** (partners and associated entities/individuals)

Level 2 actors: Co-creation process involving **other relevant actors** joining project activities when relevant and/or appropriate

Level 3 actors: Dissemination of practice-ready project results to the **'wider community of users'**

Stakeholders: Not actively engaged in the project work, but observing, and kept informed of activities and outputs

Distinguishing ‘Level 1 and 2 Actors’ is crucial for effective evaluation of the MAA

MAA elements	Level 1: Main consortium actors	Level 2: Other relevant actors
Purpose of participation	Leading and owning project activities Co-creation of practical solutions	Consultation and validation Co-creation of practical solutions Dissemination and exploitation
Level of participation	Interactive participation, acting and deciding together	Contributing, consulting, informing
Frequency of participation	Throughout the project	Periodic at specific points in project implementation
Outcome of participation	Ownership of project results	Adoption and ownership of project results

➔ It's all about the depth and frequency of the co-creation work

Step 3: Identify the relevant multi-actor-specific elements in each proposal

Proposals with a good understanding and application of the multi-actor display many characteristics depending upon the topic and project type. But there are at least four ‘**common indicators**’ to look for:

- 1) Use of appropriate terminology to describe the proposal's multi-actor approach
- 2) Practitioner-driven specific objective(s)
- 3) Practitioners' common dissemination channels
- 4) Validation and editing of practice-oriented output

Evaluators are encouraged to use these indicators to identify those elements of the proposal that are most relevant to the subsequent steps for evaluation of the multi-actor approach. More detailed guidance is provided in the **Annex** to these slides.

Step 4a: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Excellence

Excellence criterion CR 1.1	Application for MA proposals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA: Clarity and pertinence of the project's objectives, and the extent to which the proposed work is ambitious, and goes beyond the state of the art For CSA: Clarity and pertinence of the project's objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> See Requirement #1 "Objectives target users' needs" (...<i>project objectives</i>), and "Users' ...challenges and opportunities" (...<i>ambitious</i>) See Requirement #5 "...complements existing... best practices" (<i>beyond state of the art</i>)

The overarching conceptualisation of the multi-actor approach is scored as a 'Methodology' under Excellence. Similar to any other proposal methodology, the related multi-actor indicators driving the project's pathways to 'Impact' are scored under the criteria CR 1.2, CR 2.1, 2.2, 3.1, and 3.2, along with the quality and efficiency of their implementation.

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Step 4a: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Excellence

Excellence criterion CR 1.2	Application for MA proposals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA: Soundness of the proposed methodology, including the underlying concepts, models, assumptions, interdisciplinary approaches, appropriate consideration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content, and the quality of open science practices, including sharing and management of research outputs and engagement of citizens, civil society and end users where appropriate For CSA: Quality of the proposed coordination and/or support measures, including soundness of methodology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirement #2: Focusing on 'results': Conceptualisation of the proposal's MAA shows how "<i>to prepare practice-ready results</i>" Requirement #3: Conceptualisation of the proposal's MAA shows how "<i>existing/tacit practices and knowledge will be used...</i>" Requirement #4: Presentation of facilitation methods of "<i>MA engagement processes</i>" within the consortium (Level 1 actors) and for the involvement of all other relevant actors (Levels 2 & 3)

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Step 4b: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Impact

Impact criterion CR 2.1	Application for MA proposals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA/CSA: Credibility of the pathways to achieve the expected outcomes and impacts specified in the work programme, and the likely scale and significance of the contributions from the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirement #6: The proposal's pathway to impact shows how <i>“activities result in practical and ready-to-use knowledge, approaches, tools or products, that are easily accessible”</i>

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Step 4b: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Impact

Impact criterion CR 2.2	Application for MA proposals
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA/CSA: Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirement #7: A multi-actor proposal must show how <i>“these outputs will feed into the existing dissemination channels most consulted by the (end-)users in countries/regions”</i>

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Step 4c: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Quality & Effectiveness of the Implementation

Impact criterion CR 3.1	Consistency with the conceptualisation of the MAA and the envisaged impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA/CSA: Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks, and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages, and the resources overall 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The work plan mirrors the outlined conceptualisation of the multi-actor approach in Excellence. Multi-actor-related risks are included in the risk assessment Practice partners have work package or task responsibilities (Level 1 actors). Allocation of budget to the engagement of actors (Level 1 or 2) in co-creation or knowledge exchange activities (e.g. demo farms, Living Labs, or industry clusters) matches the expected Impact.

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Step 4c: Score the identified multi-actor elements under Quality & Effectiveness of the Implementation

Impact criterion CR 3.2	Consistency with the conceptualisation of the MAA and the envisaged impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RIA/IA/CSA: Capacity and role of each participant, and the extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirement #2: Focusing on "<i>Consortium composition</i>". Partner descriptions and the list of partners' achievements (Part A) represent the competencies needed to deliver the work

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Step 5a: Make final decision regarding the additional eligibility condition

- The multi-actor approach presented in a proposal needs to be suitable for the project type, topic, and objectives and methods of the proposal. Conceptualisation of the multi-actor approach **inevitably varies between proposals**, but all elements of the multi-actor approach must be woven into all parts of the application in a consistent way (Parts A & B).
- The overarching 'Conceptualisation of the MAA' is scored under Excellence in line with the other methods, concepts, models etc. outlined in the proposal.
- The seven multi-actor requirements guide the scoring of the different aspects of the multi-actor approach under each of the three evaluation criteria ('Excellence', 'Impact' and 'Quality and Effectiveness of the Implementation').
- Proposals with an incomplete, but still sufficient MAA, are scored down in the criterion that sheds light on the particular multi-actor shortcoming.
- Proposals with a lacking or misinterpreted application of the MAA must be counted as a **SIGNIFICANT WEAKNESS** under one of the criteria and trigger a below-threshold score. They do not fulfil the additional eligibility condition and are rejected.

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Step 5b: Agree on ESR statements

Good examples of ESR statements providing meaningful **positive feedback** to applicants about the completeness of the multi-actor approach in their proposals:

- *“There is a strong emphasis on user-focused, co-creative work, seeking to explore and find ways to strengthen application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA). The proposal incorporates a comprehensive range of methods to facilitate a multi-actor engagement process, e.g., stakeholder panels, collection of experiences, brokerage events, and joint development and testing of tools via co-design workshops. There is also a strong emphasis on iterative stakeholder dialogue supporting all stakeholders’ efforts (including harder to reach groups) to improve the take-up of the MAA in proposals”*
- *“The Multi-Actor Approach is very well incorporated in the different project phases, spanning the entire spectrum of co-creation, co-implementation and co-evaluation of the project activities and the different types of actors involved. End-users (rural communities and actors) and community stakeholders are explicitly indicated in the proposal as key actors for project implementation and receptors of generated solutions”*

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Step 5b: Agree on ESR statements

Good examples of ESR statements providing meaningful **negative feedback** to applicants about the completeness of the multi-actor approach in their proposals:

- *“It is a significant weakness that the methodology does not make sufficient provision for wide, multi-actor and representative inclusion, engagement or participation of rural dwellers and stakeholders as explicitly expected in the topic.”*
- *“The concept and methodology do poorly show how farmers and farmers' organisations are targeted from the planning to the execution of the project work which is a shortcoming. Overall, the project does not sufficiently show active involvement of end-users in all phases as participatory activities are foreseen for validation only. Thus, the co-creation principle is not adequately addressed. To conclude, the multi-actor approach is not sufficiently demonstrated in the concept and methodology of the project, which is a weakness.”*

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Annex: Checking for ‘common indicators’ of the multi-actor approach in proposals

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Action for indicator 1:

Search for key terms such as ‘multi-actor’, ‘interactive innovation’, ‘co-creation’, ‘stakeholder engagement’, ‘practice-ready solutions’ etc.

Is the use of key terms consistent throughout Part B?

- a) If yes, check if sentences explain the facilitation of consortium actors’ co-creation (could sit in all Part B sections)
- b) If yes, is co-creation within the consortium seen differently from other actors’/stakeholders’ involvement? (could sit in all Part B sections)
- c) If yes, is the overall conceptualisation of the MAA convincingly described in Excellence?

If yes to all of the above, the proposal’s MAA is likely to be strong and meet the additional Eligibility Condition.

However, assessment of the specific multi-actor requirements should continue when working through Parts A and B.

... more for indicator 1 and the search for key multi-actor-related terms

Do the sentences with key terms ONLY refer to external actors/stakeholders (e.g. case studies, use cases, platforms, networks, communities, clusters, dissemination activity target groups)?

If yes, it is likely that the implementation of the MAA is incomplete. A critical reflection about the integration of each multi-actor requirement into the proposal will be needed.

Is the use of the MA terminology inconsistent throughout the proposal?

If yes, evaluators should dig deeper into the overarching conceptualisation of the MAA in ‘Excellence’. If the approach still remains unclear, it is likely that the additional Eligibility Condition is not fulfilled.

For Indicator 2:

Check if one or more specific objectives emerge from the needs-driven perspective of the topic's target group(s)

For the practice-driven objective(s), identify the names of consortium partners representing each of these specific objectives (Part A).

Do these partners have Work Package (WP) or Task responsibilities?

If not, why not?

If yes, do they have sufficient resources (Person Months and duration of the WP/Task) and suitable competencies (Part A profiles/achievements and budget allocation)?

If no, it is likely that the MAA is incomplete.

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For indicator 3:

Check if the dissemination channels announced match the practice-oriented partner profiles identified for indicator 2

Is the 'plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities' (Part B – section 2.2) fully in line with the target audiences that the practice-oriented consortium partners represent? Are the selected communication and dissemination channels the most appropriate? Are the resources allocated proportionate to the proposal's ambition to benefit (end-)users?

If yes, the multi-actor requirement is likely to be fulfilled under Impact.

If no, it is likely that the multi-actor requirement might not be fully addressed under Impact. Further consideration and assessment are needed.

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For indicator 4:

Look for work steps foreseen for the validation and editing of practice-oriented outputs in Part B ‘Implementation’

Does the consortium have a partner that will coordinate a review process for the practice-oriented outputs, such as Practice Abstracts, fact sheets, handbooks, video statements, and tutorials? (Check Part B Implementation, Part A partner profile, and related budget)

Does this partner have language and journalistic skills? And will this partner, other key partners or third parties have enough time and budget allocated for the demanding production processes of high-quality practice-oriented materials?

If yes to all of the above, it is likely that the multi-actor requirements related to the practice-oriented processing of results are met.

If no, it is likely that the MAA is incomplete. Evaluators need to dig deeper for scoring the MAA and for their final assessment of the additional Eligibility Condition.

ANNEX 3: Proposed Instructions to MAA Topic Writers

This annex presents proposed instructions addressed to topic drafters / writers with indications on how to present and describe the specific need and context for the MAA in a particular topic. These instructions aim to define a short and precise text for the MAA in each topic, thus facilitating more compact topic descriptions as required from 2026.

To be included as an instruction to topic drafters / writers with a MAA condition

(This is an adaptive guidance, always confirm the use of the latest version. This version: 26.4.2025)

Following the recommendation of Focus Group on Evaluation of the MAA (Horizon PREMIERE, 2025) **all topic drafters/writers shall follow this instruction:**

The “scope” section of all topics with a MAA condition will include a paragraph, in the final part of the text, **explaining WHY the topic requires the MAA and WHAT is expected** as “genuine and sufficient involvement of a targeted array of actors” in that specific project type (RIA, IA or CSA) and topic.

This paragraph is intended to help prospective applicants on how to apply the MAA in their proposed programme of work, and to evaluators to have a clear focus of evaluation of the MAA.

The general guidance to topic drafters / writers for the MAA paragraph is **to avoid:**

- a. Include no reference to the MAA in the detail text of topic scope, as still happens with several topics in the 2025 WP.
- b. Limiting the explanation on the topic text to only a list of recommended actors to involve. This has to be part of the text but is not enough.
- c. Avoid the use of indications that are already a clear requirement of the general MAA definition and thus requested already to applicants (e.g. “The active participation and engagement of different stakeholders should span the entire project development and implementation...”).

And **to include as a minimum:**

- i. Why is this concrete topic MA? Which aspects of the 7 MAA requirements (if any) are especially relevant. Write and review the text to ensure it authenticates the need for and, the relevance of, the MAA in this topic. (This statement must be topic-specific and avoid being generalist).
- ii. Include a list of recommended (end)-users for this topic, following the same terminology as on the list of 13 user-types included in the Work Programme, plus other specific users, if any. (So far, this is the most common indication in many topic texts).
- iii. Indication, if appropriate, on the role of user-types in this specific topic, including interactive and relational dynamics between actors.
- iv. What is requested in terms of MA process (e.g. transversality, focus, social, technical, business, transformational change, practical applicability, advance innovative real-world practice). Note that all points, and particularly this one, may include reference to the RIA, IA, CSA specificity.

COMPLEMENTARY EXAMPLES

1. Example of a **better MAA text** extracted from a WP2025 topic (not including the topic title, therefore uncontextualised):
 - *Proposals must implement the 'multi-actor approach' and ensure adequate involvement of the main actors relevant for domestic plant protein feed value chain, such as farmers, other land managers, advisors, feed manufacturers, industry (including small and medium enterprises), policymakers, etc. Proposals should ensure an effective knowledge, co-creation and exchange between researchers and field actors as well as with the whole feed value chain actors concerning the benefits, challenges and opportunities of producing and integrating local protein crops for feed in the EU. To this end, proposals should develop diverse practice-oriented dissemination materials presenting R&I solutions (e.g. audiovisuals, brochures, fact sheets, etc) and should share all generated data and knowledge through existing digital tools or platforms.*
2. Common examples of how a topic currently mentions the **MAA, in a limited way** (not including the topic title, therefore uncontextualised):

- *Proposals must implement the ‘multi-actor approach’ including a range of actors to ensure that knowledge and needs from various sectors such as research, plant health services, farming/forestry sectors, advisory services, and other relevant actors of the value chain are brought together*
- *Proposals must implement the multi-actor approach to involve relevant stakeholders, in particular for the development of innovative solutions, which may include public authorities, rural communities, as well as SMEs, organisations, and social economy actors.*

3. Finally, an **example of a fictional new text** according to this instruction:

- *Proposals must implement the multi-actor approach to ensure that current research as well as traditional rural management practices of the “high altitude rural grasslands” contribute in identifying solutions to the climate challenges of their landscapes. The need for this approach is widely acknowledged in rural communities in the “high altitude” demanding action to address it. Actors to be engaged include research, plant health services, farming/forestry sectors, advisory services, and other relevant actors of the value chain. It is important to include traditional knowledge on the hands of the elder farmers and local studies groups and combine it with up-to-date research and the technical advising services to achieve a new common approach to grassland management. Activities like shared test sites, innovation-tradition workshops or design thinking could be explored.*

ANNEX 4: PROPOSED ADJUSTMENT OF THE EXISTING EVALUATION GRID FOR MAA PROPOSALS

This annex presents a proposal to include a limited extra content to the topic evaluation grid template to be used in Cluster 6 MAA topics. It is not a new and separate grid but an addition to the existing evaluation grid. The new content is highlighted in orange text in the annex.

EVALUATION GRID PREMIERE FG#2 MODEL

The following table is suggested to be integrated in the General Evaluation Grid for Horizon Cluster 6 Multi-actor topics. These indications for the evaluation of the MAA are intended to enhance and improve the evaluation in the MAA.

Notice: The initial content below is kept for the purpose of clarity on the standard template for the evaluation grid. The proposed content for the evaluation of the MAA is shown in **Orange PREMIERE colour**.

Please note this document aims to facilitate the evaluation, but the topic description in the [Work Programme](#) constitutes the legal text and should be the main reference for your assessment.

On-line topic text

XXXXXX-To be added in each topic grid

EXCELLENCE
Clarity and pertinence of the project's objectives and the extent to which the proposed work is ambitious, and goes beyond the state-of-the-art.
<i>Please address all of the following questions:</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Are the objectives clear and pertinent to the topic? 2) Is the proposed work ambitious and goes beyond the state-of-the-art?
Soundness of the proposed methodology, including the underlying concepts, models, assumptions, inter-disciplinary approaches, and the quality of open science practices, including sharing and management of research outputs and engagement of citizens, civil society and end users where appropriate. Multi-actor approach specificities.
<i>Please address all of the following 6 questions to assess the scientific methodology and the quality of open science practices:</i>

- Is the **scientific methodology** (i.e. the **concepts**, models and assumptions that underpin the work) clear and sound?
- Is the **proposed work interdisciplinary**?

For instance, is it clear how expertise and methods from different disciplines will be brought together and integrated in pursuit of the objectives?

Please do not comment here on the expertise of the consortium, but on the proposed work

- Are **Open Science practices implemented** as an integral part of the proposed methodology?
- Since **the Multi-actor approach is required**, has this instrument been taken appropriately and comprehensively into account in the proposed work, from development of the project idea to all phases of implementation?

With a focus on evaluation in Excellence, please have a comprehensive view into the whole project proposal, including budget and consortium composition, when evaluating the quality of the multi-actor approach.

For instance:

-Is it clear that the co-creation applies to all the project lifecycle, starting with the idea, and the actors involved are adequate and have a clear role all along the project? Is the balance of actors adequate for the type of project (CSA, IA, RIA)?

-Will the results be targeted to users, using also existing practices and tacit knowledge?

-Are methods, expertise and engagement of all actors involved clearly demonstrated? Will the project results be practical, ready to use, understandable and accessible?

-Overall, is this multi-actor approach feasible?

*--please note that in the evidence of an insufficient multi-actor approach in the proposal this has to be considered and rated as a **Significant weakness**.*

--please include here further references regarding the MAA included in the topic text-

Beyond this point of the evaluation grid, no further add-ons are proposed and the current grid maintains its content.

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